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Title: Multidimensional reference points for health and money and their relation to subjective well-being

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: The nature and origin of reference points in human decision making remain important research topics. We are using Multi Discrepancies Theory (MDT) to empirically investigate whether multiple reference points regarding income and health are associated with the subjective well-being (SWB) of individuals. This knowledge improves the understanding of which reference points may be relevant in self-assessments of wellbeing.

Methods: We measured SWB in a representative sample (N=550). Subjects were asked to complete the Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS) to assess to what extent they agreed with five propositions about their life. For the income-related reference points, we elicited the monthly household income and asked subjects to indicate how they assessed their income compared to

several reference points (self-needs, self-deserves, self-wants, self-others, self-past, self-progress and self-future). These questions were derived from MDT and were also asked for health.

Results: We found a negative convex relationship between SWLS and age. In line with the literature, happiness was increasing with income and health, and lower for unemployed people. Our results showed that SWB was most strongly associated with people's comparison of their income to their needs (self-needs), their progression over time compared to past expectations (self-progress), and for health also to what they felt to deserve (self-deserves). Hence, it seems these discrepancies are used as reference points and matter more for happiness than the other included comparisons.

Discussion: Our research suggests that multidimensional reference points are associated with subjective well-being scores. We find significant negative associations between the SWLS and discrepancies between self-needs or self-progress for both income and health. This suggests that relative changes in income/health may affect well-being and that people use several reference points in assessing SWB. Interestingly, comparisons of health with others appeared less influential for SWLS. These findings have important implications for both research and policy.